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Susceptibility of Lion's paw scallop (*Nodipecten subnodosus*) juveniles to a *pirAB*-positive *Vibrio campbellii* strain isolated from *Litopenaeus vannamei* shrimp affected by Acute Hepatopancreatic Necrosis Disease (AHPND)

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ABSTRACT

Acute hepatopancreatic necrosis disease (AHPND) is a serious bacterial infection affecting penaeid shrimp, caused primarily by *Vibrio* species harboring the *pirAB* toxin genes. While AHPND has been studied extensively in shrimp, its potential impact on other marine invertebrates remains largely unexplored. This study evaluates, for the first time, the susceptibility of juvenile lion's paw scallops (*Nodipecten subnodosus*) to AHPND-associated *Vibrio campbellii* ($v_{CAHPND-VP3}$) strains isolated from *Litopenaeus vannamei* shrimp outbreaks. Experimental infection by immersion assays demonstrated a dose-dependent response, with 100 % cumulative mortality at 5×10^6 CFU/mL, while lower concentrations resulted in subclinical infections. The presence of $v_{CAHPND-VP3}$ in gill and stomach tissues was confirmed by nested PCR detection of *pirAB* genes. Comparative pathogenicity assays between $v_{CAHPND-VP3}$ and the native *Vibrio alginolyticus* strain revealed that, despite similar rates of bacterial uptake, only $v_{CAHPND-VP3}$ caused high mortality, highlighting the critical role of PirAB toxins in virulence. Whole genome sequencing of the $v_{CAHPND-VP3}$ strain confirmed the presence of the *pirAB*-carrying plasmid, previously reported as pVA1 and revealed additional genes associated with pathogenicity and mobile genetic elements. These results confirm the susceptibility of mollusk species to AHPND-associated *Vibrio* and highlight potential ecological risks related to the dissemination of *pirAB*-positive vibrios in coastal environments.

1. Introduction

The scallop *Nodipecten subnodosus*, commonly known as the “Lion's paw”, is distributed in tropical and subtropical waters of the eastern Pacific, from Mexico to Peru (Keen, 1971). As one of the largest scallop

species, it can reach a shell height of up to 218 mm (Felix Paico et al., 1999) and an adductor muscle weight of up to 150 g, making it highly desirable for the “Jumbo scallop” market (Koch et al., 2005, Chávez-Villalba and Cáceres-Martínez, 1992). This species typically inhabits coastal ecosystems such as bays, lagoons, and channels, at depths

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reaching up to 110 m, forming natural beds with low organism densities (<2 individuals m²) (Ponce-Díaz et al., 2011). However, natural populations are scarce, which limits harvesting potential (García-Domínguez et al., 1992). In addition, natural larval collection yields are remarkably low. For example, densities of less than 1.7 larvae per collector have been reported in Mexican regions such as Bahía Concepción and Loreto in the Gulf of California (Arellano Martínez et al., 2011; Félix et al., 1999) and Laguna Ojo de Liebre on the Pacific coast (Maguiño Napurí et al., 2011).

These limitations highlight the potential of this species for aquaculture (Maeda Martínez and Lodeiros Seijo, 2011) and have led to the development of larval production protocols under laboratory conditions (Villavicencio Peralta, 1997; Racotta et al., 2003; Ramírez Arce, 2009; Maeda Martínez & Lodeiros Seijo, 2011).

In South America, laboratory-based seed production has been conducted in Ecuador in 2019 (Revilla et al., 2019) and in Peru since 2021 (Diringer et al., 2021). The latter experience also evaluated seed growth and fattening in long-line systems in both mangrove and open-sea environments. However, significant mortality events, primarily linked to bacterial pathogens, have hindered the commercial scalability of *N. subnodosus* aquaculture in the region (Diringer et al., 2021).

Marine bivalve mollusks accumulate diverse bacterial microbiota due to their filter-feeding behavior, making them particularly susceptible to bacterial pathogens (Beaz-Hidalgo et al., 2010). Numerous bacterial diseases have been documented in larvae, juveniles and adults, affecting both wild and cultured populations, generating a latent risk for aquaculture (Zannella et al., 2017). Key bacterial pathogens include genera *Vibrio*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Aeromonas* species, which can cause severe mortality (Mendoza-Maldonado et al., 2018; Guo and Ford, 2016; Travers et al., 2015; Prado et al., 2014). In *N. subnodosus*, laboratory-produced veliger larvae have shown high susceptibility to *Vibrio alginolyticus* strain APSA2 isolated from white shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) post larvae, with 100 % mortality at 10⁵ cells/ml within 2 days (Luna-González et al., 2002). Additionally, adults exposed to the same pathogenic strain exhibit two main immune responses: hemocyte activation and lysosomal enzyme production (Ramírez-Castillo et al., 2011). No mortality was observed in adult scallops, thus suggesting a developmental stage-dependent pathogenicity.

Acute Hepatopancreatic Necrosis Disease (AHPND), also known as early mortality syndrome (EMS), is a bacterial infection that severely impacts farmed shrimp populations, generating considerable economic losses worldwide (Kumar et al., 2021, Flegel, 2019). AHPND was primarily associated with *Vibrio* species, particularly *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* (v_PAHPND). However, other etiological agents such as *V. harveyi* in Thailand (Kondo et al., 2015), *V. owensii* in China (Liu et al., 2015), *V. punensis* in South America (Restrepo et al., 2018) and *V. campbellii* in China (Dong et al., 2017a) and Mexico (Soto-Rodríguez et al., 2024) have also been identified. These pathogenic strains share a common feature: the presence of the pVA1 plasmid (63–70 kb) which encodes homologs of the *Photobacterium* PirA and PirB toxins associated with virulence and toxicity in insects (Dong et al., 2017b; Lee et al., 2015; Tran et al., 2013).

Since its initial outbreak in China in 2009, AHPND has rapidly spread to other countries, reaching Mexico in 2013 and South America in 2016, including Peru (WOAH, 2023; Pretell et al., 2020). To date, only cultured penaeids are known to be naturally affected by AHPND, with *Litopenaeus vannamei* and *Penaeus monodon* being the most susceptible species (WOAH, 2023; De La Peña et al., 2015). The disease mainly affects larvae and juveniles, with the hepatopancreas, stomach, and gut being the affected organs (WOAH, 2023; Han et al., 2015). AHPND is transmitted horizontally, either orally or through cohabitation (WOAH, 2023; Yu et al., 2022). However, experimental evidence indicates that bivalves such as the Catarina scallop (*Argopecten ventricosus*) are susceptible to *V. parahaemolyticus* strains carrying the AHPND plasmid. In immersion challenges, seeds showed 100 % mortality within 96 h, while adults reached 80 % mortality by 144 h. Histopathological lesions in

adults were evident as early as 24 h post-infection, including epithelial desquamation and hemocyte infiltration in digestive tissues (Mendoza-Maldonado et al., 2018).

In Peru, shrimp aquaculture is often integrated into coastal ecosystems, where farms intake water and discharge effluent, usually without prior treatment (Lightner et al., 2012). This practice raises concerns about the potential transfer of bacterial pathogens from shrimp farms to wild and farmed bivalve populations, including *N. subnodosus*, which susceptibility has never been investigated. In this context, the present study aimed to evaluate the susceptibility of *N. subnodosus*. We compared juveniles experimentally infected with either a *V. campbellii* strain causing AHPND (v_CAHPND-VP3), or with a strain of *V. alginolyticus* P12 isolated from wild broodstock of *N. subnodosus*. We also determined the presence of v_CAHPND-VP3 in specific organs by molecular detection of the *pirAB* gene, performed whole genome sequencing (WGS) and comparative genomic analysis of the *V. campbellii* VP3 strain to characterize virulence and evaluate the potential role of *N. subnodosus* as a reservoir of the pathology in Peruvian coastal ecosystems.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Juveniles *N. subnodosus*

Juveniles *N. subnodosus* were produced at the Centro Colectivo Educativo Experimental de Biología y Biotecnología Acuática y Acuicola de Puerto Pizarro – CEBAP (3° 30' 07" S, 80° 23' 42" W), located in the department of Tumbes, Peru. The process covered the postlarval stage (5 mm) to over 20 mm valvar height, maintaining controlled conditions at 28 °C and salinity of 32 ppm.

A total of 240 individuals were selected; of which 120 were used for susceptibility testing and 90 for pathogenicity comparison (Table 1). A further 30 individuals were used to evaluate assimilation rates of v_CAHPND-VP3 and *V. alginolyticus* P12 by *N. subnodosus*. The juveniles' scallops were fed a 1:1 mixture of *Isochrysis galbana* and *Chaetoceros calcitrans* in three daily rations of 1.0 × 10⁷ cells/scallop/day. The susceptibility assay assessed the response of *N. subnodosus* juveniles to increasing concentrations of *V. campbellii* associated with AHPND (trial 1), while the pathogenicity comparison (trial 2) examined mortality and bacterial assimilation rates following exposure to *V. campbellii* associated with AHPND and *V. alginolyticus* at an established concentration (see section 2.5 for details).

2.2. Bacterial isolation

The AHPND-associated *V. campbellii* VP3 strain (v_CAHPND-VP3) was isolated during the summer of 2024 from moribund whiteleg shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) collected from an intensive culture pond in Tumbes, Peru. The isolation was performed on animals exhibiting gross AHPND symptoms. Macerated hepatopancreas tissue (50 g) was seeded in Tryptic Soy Broth plus 2 % NaCl (TSB + 2 %NaCl) and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. Subsequently, colonies were isolated on Thiosulfate Citrate Bile Sucrose (TCBS) agar plates (Liofilchen, Italy) and HiCrome *Vibrio* Agar (HIMEDIA, India).

During the summer of 2020, four strain native *Vibrio* bacteria (P1, P5, P10, P12) were also isolated from a pool of three healthy wild adults of *N. subnodosus* larger than 100 mm. Stomach tissue (100 mg) was

Table 1
Biometric parameters of *Nodipecten subnodosus* juveniles used in susceptibility (Trial 1) and pathogenicity (Trial 2) assays.

Challenge	Valvar height mm			weight g		
	Mean ± sd	Max.	Min	Mean ± sd	Max.	Min
Trial 1	24.7 ± 0.84	29.5	20.4	4.5 ± 1	6.5	3.4
Trial 2	23.8 ± 0.5	26.1	22.1	4.3 ± 1	6.1	3.3

macerated and cultured on TSB + 2 % NaCl, followed by colony isolation on TCBS agar. Isolated strains were stored at -20°C in 10 % (V/V) glycerol.

2.3. DNA extraction and molecular characterization

Selected strains (P1, P5, P10, P12, and νC AHPND-VP3) were sub-cultured in 1 mL of TSB + 2 % NaCl and incubated at 30°C for 20 h under constant shaking. Cultures were centrifuged at 13,000 rpm for 5 min. For the amplification of specific genes, DNA was extracted from the resulting pellets using a modified 2 % CTAB protocol (Coffroth et al., 1992) supplemented with 0.2 % β -mercaptoethanol and 2 μL of Proteinase K (Thermo Scientific, Germany). DNA purification was performed with a phenol:chloroform:isoamyl alcohol mixture (20:24:1), followed by isopropanol precipitation (2 volumes, -20°C) and resuspension in 1X TE buffer. Residual RNA was removed by RNase treatment at 37°C for 30 min (Thermo Scientific, Germany).

The capacity of *Vibrio* isolates to induce AHPND was determined by the amplification of the PirAB toxin sequence using the nested PCR protocol recommended by the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) (Dangtip et al. 2015). Molecular characterization of the five isolated bacterial strains also included the amplification of the 16S rRNA gene with universal primers 27F and 1492R and subsequent sequencing with internal primers 518F and 800R (Gonzales et al., 2021).

For whole-genome sequencing (WGS) of the νC AHPND-VP3, genomic DNA was extracted from bacterial pellets using the ZymoBIOMICS DNA Miniprep Kit (D4300, Zymo Research, USA) after a 30 min incubation at 37°C with Proteinase K (D3001-2-20, Zymo Research, USA), following the protocol described by Cusimano et al. (2025). DNA concentration and purity were evaluated using a Qubit fluorometer with the dsDNA HS Assay Kit (Q32851, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) and an NP80 spectrophotometer. Library preparation was performed with the Native Barcoding Kit 24 V14 (SQK-NBD114.24, Oxford Nanopore Technologies, UK), using 400 ng of input DNA for end-repair and dA-tailing with the NEBNext FFPE DNA Repair Mix and End Repair/dA-Tailing Module. Barcode ligation was carried out using Blunt/TA Ligase Master Mix, followed by adapter ligation with NEBNext Quick T4 DNA Ligase. Prepared libraries were purified with AMPure XP beads (A63880, Beckman Coulter, USA), quantified by fluorometry, and 100 fmol were loaded onto R10.4.1 flow cells (FLO-MIN114, ONT, UK). Sequencing was performed on a MinION Mk1B platform using MinKNOW software, with data collected in fast5 format according to the manufacturer's instructions (Hong et al., 2024).

2.4. Preparation of inoculates

Inoculum preparation was performed by seeding 100 μL strains onto TSA + 2 % NaCl plates for 24 h at 37°C . The suspension of each bacterial strain selected: both native (*V. alginolyticus* strain P12) and pathogenic (νC AHPND-VP3), was obtained by washing the surface of the plate with 2 % saline solution. The cell density of the bacterial suspensions was spectrophotometrically determined at a wavelength of 600 nm (OD600) using a nanophotometer. A concentration of 5.1×10^8 CFU/mL was obtained for νC AHPND-VP3 and 4.5×10^8 CFU/mL for *V. alginolyticus* strain P12 at OD600 = 1.2. The inoculum was stored at 4°C for 2 h before the experimental infection.

2.5. Immersion challenge

2.5.1. Trial 1: AHPND susceptibility assay

Susceptibility of juvenile *N. subnodosus* to the νC AHPND-VP3 was evaluated through an immersion challenge. Experimental treatments included four groups in triplicate, with 10 individuals per replicate. Specimens were conditioned for 72 h in containers with 6 L of filtrated and UV treated seawater under controlled conditions of salinity 35 ppt, pH 8.4, temperature 23.6°C ($\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$), and dissolved oxygen ≥ 5 mg/L.

Subsequently, the experimental groups were exposed by immersion to three final concentrations of the pathogen: T1 = control without bacterial inoculation, T2 = 5×10^2 , T3 = 5×10^4 and T4 = 5×10^6 CFU/mL following the methodologies described by Devadas et al. (2018). Feeding was performed every two days with a 1:1 mixture of *I. galbana* and *C. calcitrans* at 1×10^9 cells/mL. Tanks were cleaned daily by siphoning from the third day onwards. Mortality was monitored every 3 h for 15 consecutive days. Dead animals were immediately removed upon observation and gill and stomach tissues were removed and preserved separately in absolute ethanol for subsequent molecular analysis.

2.5.2. Trial 2: bacterial assimilation and comparative pathogenicity assays

To evaluate the bacterial assimilation capacity of *N. subnodosus*, juveniles were first exposed to νC AHPND-VP3 and *V. alginolyticus* strain P12 under controlled conditions. Animals were placed in plastic containers at a density of two individuals per 1.2 L, and each container was inoculated separately with either νC AHPND-VP3 or *V. alginolyticus* strain P12 at a final concentration of 5×10^6 CFU/mL. Bacterial uptake was assessed by quantitative water sampling every 30 min over 6 h. Colony-forming units (CFU/mL) were quantified by seeding on TCBS agar. After 6 h, the gill and stomach tissues were collected and preserved in absolute ethanol. Assimilation of νC AHPND-VP3 was further confirmed by nested PCR amplification targeting the *pirAB* toxin genes.

Subsequently, the pathogenicity of νC AHPND-VP3 was compared to that of the native *V. alginolyticus* strain in juvenile *N. subnodosus*. Ten conditioned animals were randomly distributed into nine plastic containers (6 L of seawater per container) and assigned in triplicate to two treatments and a control group. Treatments consisted of exposure to νC AHPND-VP3 or *V. alginolyticus* strain P12, both at a final concentration of 5×10^6 CFU/mL, while the control group remained unexposed. Mortality was monitored every 3 h for 15 days, and dead animals were immediately removed and their gill tissues preserved in absolute ethanol for qPCR analysis.

2.6. Pathogen detection by nested PCR

At the end of the infection trials, gill tissues were collected and preserved in absolute ethanol. DNA extraction was performed on pooled samples consisting of two individuals per tissue type, each pool derived from a single replicate tank. For treatments T1, T2, and T3, five pooled gill samples were processed per group. In treatment T4, five pooled samples were extracted for both gill and stomach tissues. DNA was extracted using the ZymoBIOMICS™ DNA Miniprep Kit (Zymo Research, USA), following the manufacturer's instructions. Detection of the *pirAB* gene was carried out by nested PCR according to Dangtip et al., (2015) and was applied to both infected and control groups. To assess DNA quality and confirm the presence of *Vibrio* spp., amplification of the 16S rRNA gene was performed in all samples (Frank et al., 2008).

2.7. Quantification by qPCR

The PCR primers and TaqMan probe for the detection of the virulence plasmid pAHPND/EMS (GenBank NZ_CP047987.1, Fu et al., 2020) were selected from the *pirA*-like gene (position 22475–22743). The upstream (VpPirA-F: 5'-TTG GAC TGT CGA ACC AAA CG-3') and downstream (VpPirA-R: 5'-GCA CCC CAT TGG TAT TGA ATG-3') primers were used to amplify a DNA fragment of 284 bp. The TaqMan VpPirA probe (5'-AGA CAG CAA ACA TAC ACC TAT CAT CCC GGA-3') was synthesized and labeled with 6-carboxyfluorescein (FAM) on the 5' end and N,N,N',N'-tetramethyl-6-carboxyrhododamine (TAMRA) on the 3' end. For the qPCR assay, the BIOLAN- AHPND qPCR (NATGEN, Peru) was used. 2 μL of DNA (20 ng DNA per μL) extracted from the samples was added to a qPCR mix containing a 1x concentration of master mix, 0.3 μM of each primer, and 0.15 μM of TaqMan probe to a final volume of 20 μL . The qPCR profile consisted of 5 min at 95°C followed by 40 cycles of 15 s at 95°C and 1 min at 60°C . Amplification detection for

fluorescence and data analysis for qPCR assays were performed using the micPCR system (bms, Australia). The standard curve for absolute quantification was generated using five-fold dilutions in duplicate of pVcPirA-1 plasmid DNA (*V. campbellii* plasmid DNA). The concentrations used ranged from 1×10^1 to 1×10^6 copies/ μ L. For each qPCR assay, raw fluorescence data were acquired in real time per cycle and processed using the micPCR kit software, applying a specific baseline threshold for the detection of the FAM fluorophore. The quantification cycle (Cq) values were determined automatically, and the plasmid copy number in the experimental samples was estimated by interpolation from the standard curve. For each infection assay (Trial 2), a single pooled gill sample from two individuals was analyzed by adding *N. subnodosus* DNA.

2.8. Statistical analysis

Bacterial assimilation was evaluated by analyzing the reduction in bacterial concentration over time in the water using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey's post hoc test. Before analysis, the Shapiro-Wilk test was applied to assess data normality, and Bartlett's test was used to verify the homogeneity of variances. The data were log-transformed to meet these assumptions and normalize the distribution (\log_{10}). The sensitivity of juveniles was assessed using a completely randomized design, while differences between treatments were analyzed with the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test, followed by Dunn's post hoc test.

The pathogenicity of the v_CAHPND-VP3 strain was evaluated with the cumulative mortality among the three treatments (administered at a dose of 5×10^6 CFU/mL) were monitored. Since the data did not meet the assumptions of normality and homoscedasticity, a Kruskal-Wallis test was employed. Mortality rates were calculated as the median of triplicate replicates for each treatment over 15 days. All statistical analyses and visualizations were conducted in RStudio (v.4.2.0) using the ggplot2 and stats packages.

2.9. Bioinformatic analysis

Phylogenetic analysis was conducted to determine the evolutionary relationships among the *Vibrio* sequences analyzed in this study. Sequences were first edited using BioEdit following quality control assessment, and BLASTn searches against the NCBI nucleotide database preliminarily confirmed taxonomic identity. Multiple sequence alignments were performed with ClustalW, and phylogenetic trees were constructed using the Maximum Likelihood (ML) method under either the Tamura-Nei or General Time Reversible (GTR) model, depending on the lowest Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) score. Tree robustness was evaluated through 1,000 bootstrap replicates. The resulting phylogenetic tree was annotated and visualized to highlight clustering patterns of the isolate with closely related *Vibrio* taxa.

Whole-genome sequencing and bioinformatic analysis of the v_CAHPND-VP3 strain were conducted using Oxford Nanopore Technologies. Raw FAST5 files were base called with Guppy v6.5.7 in super accuracy (SUP) mode to generate FASTQ sequences. Adapter and barcode sequences were removed using Porechop v0.2.4 (<https://github.com/rrwick/Porechop>). Quality filtering was performed with NanoFilt v2.8.0 (De Coster et al., 2018), retaining reads with an average quality score ≥ 14 and length ≥ 1000 bp. Read quality metrics were assessed with NanoPlot v1.44.1 (De Coster and Rademakers, 2023).

De novo assembly was performed using Flye (Kolmogorov et al., 2019). Assembly integrity and contamination were evaluated with CheckM (Parks et al., 2015) using Vibrionaceae-specific marker genes. Taxonomic identity was confirmed by extracting rRNA genes with Barrnap (<https://github.com/tseemann/barrnap>); the 16S rRNA gene was submitted to the EzBioCloud identification platform (<https://www.ezbiocloud.net/identify>) and compared against the NCBI core nucleotide database (Johnson et al., 2008). Phylogenetic relationships were

inferred using MEGA 12 (Kumar et al., 2024) via the maximum likelihood method based on EzBioCloud 16S sequences.

Genomes of the closest related strains were retrieved from NCBI and compared by average nucleotide identity (ANI) using ANIclustermap (<https://github.com/moshi4/ANIclustermap>). Plasmids were identified with PlasmidFinder v2.1.6 (Carattoli and Hasman, 2020), and their mobility was assessed using MOB-suite v3.1.4 (<https://github.com/phac-nml/mob-suite>).

Genome annotation was performed with Prokka v1.14.6 (Seemann, 2014) under default parameters. Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and virulence genes were identified using CARD-RGI v6.0.3 and Abriicate v1.0.1 (<https://github.com/tseemann/abriicate>), querying the CARD (Jia et al., 2016) and VFDB (Chen et al., 2005) databases, respectively. Only hits with ≥ 90 % identity and ≥ 80 % coverage were retained.

Mobile genetic elements, including insertion sequences, transposons, and plasmids, were detected using MobileElementFinder v1.1.2 (<https://pypi.org/project/MobileElementFinder/>). Circular genome representations and COG-based functional annotations were generated with GenoVi v0.2.16 (Cumsille et al., 2023). Plasmids carrying AMR and virulence genes were visualized using SnapGene v8.0 (www.snapgene.com).

3. Results

3.1. Bacterial isolation and molecular characterization

The presence of *pirAB* gene was confirmed in v_CAHPND-VP3 isolated from the hepatopancreas of moribund shrimp. This strain produces typical deep green colonies on TCBS. Additionally, four *Vibrio* strains were isolated from apparently healthy *N. subnodosus* adults. Three strains (P5, P10, P12) were identified as *V. alginolyticus*, while one strain (P1) was identified as *V. parahaemolyticus*. None of these strains harbored the *pirAB* gene associated with AHPND.

The multilocus sequence analysis, based on the conserved 16S rRNA genes, reveals a close phylogenetic relationship between v_CAHPND VP3 strain (Genbank accession number PV217812) and the v_CAHPND BB120 strain previously reported in outbreaks in Ecuador shrimp farms. This relationship shows high phylogenetic support, with a bootstrap value of 75. A phylogenetic connection is evident between these strains and isolates of *V. alginolyticus* (strains P12, P5 and P10) and *V. parahaemolyticus* (strain P1) obtained from *N. subnodosus*. see Fig. 1

Genome-wide comparison using the Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) metric, confirmed that v_CAHPND-VP3 strain (referred to as *V. campbellii* kriznoit in Fig. 3) shares ≥ 97 % nucleotide identity with *V. campbellii* reference genomes, supporting its classification within this specie. ANI values below 85 % were observed between v_CAHPND-VP3 and other *Vibrio* species (*V. alginolyticus*, *V. parahaemolyticus*, and *V. rotiferianus*), confirming their phylogenetic divergence see Fig. 2.

Analysis of the complete genome of v_CAHPND-VP3 shows two circular chromosomes measuring 3.62 Mb and 2.22 Mb, respectively in line with the bipartite genome structure commonly described in AHPND-causing *Vibrio* strains (Dong et al., 2017c; Wang et al., 2020). The annotated coding sequences (CDSs), classified into functional categories according to the Clusters of Orthologous Groups (COGs) classification, include genes involved in cellular processes, metabolism, information storage and processing, as well as a considerable number of hypothetical proteins (Fig. 3). In addition, four extrachromosomal replicon elements ranging in size from 22.42 Kb to 73.42 Kb were identified. These replicons present coding for mobilization proteins, conjugation systems and hypothetical proteins. The distribution of GC content and GC bias shows regional variations in sequence composition, potentially linked to genomic islands or horizontal acquisition of virulence determinants consistent with the structure observed in bacterial plasmids.

The pVA1-kriznoit plasmid (73,423 bp) of v_CAHPND-VP3 strain encodes the *pirA* and *pirB* toxin genes, flanked by IS5 transposases and hypothetical proteins (Fig. 4). Genes associated with conjugative

Fig. 1. Phylogenetic tree inferred using the Maximum Likelihood method based on the Tamura-Nei model. Bootstrap support values $\geq 70\%$ at major nodes are shown. The scale bar indicates the number of nucleotide substitutions per site. Strains used in experimental pathogenicity assays are shown in bold; the host species from which each strain was isolated is indicated in parentheses.

transfer were also identified, including a replicon, a relaxase and several components of the type IV secretion system (T4SS) such as *virB1* to *virB10*, *traF* and *traC*. The plasmid also contains genes encoding putative pilus assembly proteins (*pilN*, *pilQ*), as well as other elements such as topB, N-6 DNA methylase and a site-specific recombinase (recombinase F), which may contribute to plasmid stability and integration. This organization reflects a modular structure with regions associated with virulence, mobilization and maintenance.

Comparative genomic analysis of the AHPND-associated plasmids (pVA1-kriznoit, pVA1-3HP and pVpR14) revealed highly conserved structural elements, including the *pirA* and *pirB* toxin genes, IS5 transposases and adjacent hypothetical proteins (Fig. 5). The *pirAB* operon is flanked by IS5 transposases in all three plasmids, suggesting a conserved mobile virulence cassette. In particular, pVA1-kriznoit and pVA1-3HP exhibit identical architecture and size (5,427 bp) within this region, indicating a high degree of conservation between *V. campbellii* and *V. parahaemolyticus* plasmids. The *pirA* and *pirB* toxin genes are flanked by IS5 transposases in all three plasmids, forming a conserved transposable cassette that may promote recombination with other plasmids or genomic regions. In addition, the presence of a relaxase and replicon in pVA1-kriznoit supports its capacity for autonomous conjugative transfer. Altogether, these features reflect the genomic plasticity of *v_CAHPND-VP3* and its potential role as a reservoir and vector for the dissemination of AHPND-associated virulence factors among *Vibrio* species.

3.2. Trial 1: AHPND susceptibility assay

The sensitivity challenge of *Nodipecten subnodosus* juveniles to *v_CAHPND-VP3* was analyzed using the Kruskal–Wallis test, which yielded a significant overall statistic ($H = 30.015$, $p = 1.209 \times 10^{-7}$). Post hoc comparisons indicated that only treatment T4 (5×10^6 CFU/mL) differed significantly from the other groups, confirming that this was the sole dose associated with statistically significant mortality. For T4, mortalities started at the sixth day post-infection, with an initial mortality of 16.7 % that reached 100 % cumulative mortality by day 15 (Fig. 6). No mortality was observed in T3 (5×10^4 CFU/mL) and T2 (5×10^2 CFU/mL).

From day 4 post-infection, *N. subnodosus* juveniles exposed to T4 treatment (5×10^6 CFU/mL) showed signs of lethargy and stopped feeding. Progressive tissue damage was observed in the mantle,

characterized by pallor, retraction, and epithelial sloughing. Gill filaments appeared disorganized, with clear evidence of lamellar fusion and partial collapse of the respiratory lamellae. These lesions culminated in mass mortality by day 15 post-infection (Fig. 6). This symptomatic pattern is consistent with the typical response of bivalves to severe bacterial infections. In contrast, no mortality was observed in treatments T2 (5×10^2 CFU/mL) and T3 (5×10^4 CFU/mL). However, nested PCR confirmed the presence of the *pirAB* gene in gill tissues from both groups, indicating subclinical infections. In treatment T4, nested PCR was conducted on five pooled samples from both gill and stomach tissues. The *pirAB* gene was detected in 100 % of gill samples and in 40 % of stomach samples (Supplementary Fig. S1; Table 2). Additionally, all pooled samples from all treatments (T1–T4), regardless of tissue type, tested positive for the 16S rRNA gene, confirming successful DNA amplification and *Vibrio* detection.

3.3. Trial 2: bacterial assimilation and comparative pathogenicity assays

Complete assimilation of the bacterial inoculum was observed after 150 min, with no significant differences between the native *V. alginolyticus* strain P12 and the *v_CAHPND-VP3*. Monitoring was extended to 360 min to ensure the absence of bacterial regrowth (Fig. 7). The assimilation of *v_CAHPND-VP3* was further confirmed by nested PCR detection of the *pirAB* gene in gill tissue, and to a lesser extent in stomach tissue. The 16S rRNA gene was used as an internal control (Supplementary Table S1 and Supplementary Fig. S2).

Pathogenicity was confirmed in treatments exposed to 5×10^6 CFU/mL of *V. campbellii*, the causative agent of AHPND, with mortality observed from day 5 under controlled environmental conditions and reaching 100 % cumulative mortality by day 15. In contrast, exposure to 5×10^6 CFU/mL of *Vibrio alginolyticus* resulted in cumulative mortality of 30 % by day 15, with mortality observed from day 9. No mortalities were observed in the uninfected control group (See Fig. 8).

3.4. PirAB plasmid quantification by qPCR

To evaluate the sensitivity of the qPCR technique, we used the plasmid pVcPirA-1, which encodes the *pirAB* gene associated with Acute Hepatopancreatic Necrosis Disease (AHPND). The standard curve was generated by successive dilution from 1×10^6 to 1×10^1 copies/ μ L of the plasmid. The average regression coefficient obtained for the

Fig. 3. Circular genome map of *Vibrio campbellii* strain VP3. The upper panel corresponds to the two circular chromosomes, while the lower panel represents the four plasmids detected. The outer rings show the coding sequences annotated on the forward and reverse strands, color-coded by functional categories according to the Clusters of Orthologues Groups (COG) classification. Inner rings show variations in GC content, indicating regions of sequence heterogeneity.

standard curves was 0.99, reflecting a high linearity and an efficiency of 0.97. The detection limit of the qPCR method was estimated to be less than 10 copies of the plasmid in duplicate analysis (Supplementary Fig. S3).

Real-time TaqMan probe PCR targeting PirA toxin was used to determine the number of copies/ μ l of the PirAB plasmid and the presence of ν_C AHPND-VP3. Quantification was performed from the inoculum (CFU/mL) in water to verify the exposure concentrations of the animals, as well as from the gill tissue pool of moribund and surviving juveniles at the end of trial 2, corresponding to 15 days post-infection (Table 3).

The detection of the virulence plasmid in the inoculum and in the

water at day 0 evidenced a lower concentration of copies/ μ l, in relation to the CFU/mL of inoculated bacteria. In addition, the lethal plasmid load, equivalent to 1.4×10^6 copies/ μ l, was detected early in the threshold cycle (Ct) 17, correlating with the mortality observed in specimens exposed to this high concentration (Table 2). In contrast, sublethal concentrations, detected in surviving individuals, were 5.5×10^3 copies/ μ l and 1.3×10^2 copies/ μ l, corresponding to Ct values of 24 and 29, respectively (Table 3). These results revealed a significantly lower bacterial load in organisms exposed to lower doses, consistent with reduced pathogenic impact.

Fig. 2. Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) heatmap and hierarchical clustering of *Vibrio* spp. isolates, including *Vibrio campbellii* VP3, a strain carrying the kriznoit plasmid associated with Acute Hepatopancreatic Necrosis Disease (AHPND). The heatmap displays a color gradient representing genomic similarity, where red indicates high ANI values ($\geq 97\%$), supporting species-level identity, and green denotes lower values ($< 90\%$), indicative of interspecific divergence. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

4. Discussion

The pVAHPND plasmid, responsible for AHPND via the production of PirAB toxins, is highly prevalent in *V. parahaemolyticus* and *V. campbellii* strains in Latin America (Han et al., 2017; Soto-Rodríguez et al., 2024). Thus, untreated effluents from shrimp farms represent a critical risk factor for the surrounding biodiversity, in particular during AHPND outbreaks where farmers are used to increase water renewal (Lee et al., 2002; Manchanayake et al., 2023; Sanches-Fernandes et al., 2022).

Whole genome sequencing of *v*_CAHPND-VP3 confirmed its identity based on ANI values $\geq 97\%$ with *V. campbellii* reference genomes, while

ANI values $< 85\%$ with *V. alginolyticus* and *V. parahaemolyticus* supported its clear phylogenetic separation from other *Vibrio* species (Bao et al., 2022; Vandeputte et al., 2024). The recovery of the full genome structure, including both chromosomes and all plasmids was enabled by long-read sequencing using Oxford Nanopore technology, which overcomes the limitations of short-read platforms like Illumina, particularly in resolving repetitive regions and large structural elements (Giordano et al., 2017; Wick et al., 2017). This level of resolution is critical for accurate identification and characterization of multipartite genomes, such as those found in *Vibrio* spp., which typically comprise two chromosomes and a variable number of plasmids (Dong et al., 2019; Wang

Fig. 4. Plasmid map of pVA1-kriznoit (73,423 bp) identified in *Vibrio campbellii* VP3 isolated from moribund specimens of *Litopenaeus vannamei* in samples from Tumbes. Arrows indicate predicted open reading frames (ORFs), with their direction representing the transcriptional orientation of each gene. Functional gene categories are color-coded: *pirA* and *pirB* (yellow), IS5 transposases, recombinase (*TnpA*, *TnpR*, Recombinase F), and N-6 DNA methylase (pink and cyan), conjugation-related genes including replicon, relaxase, *traF*, *traC*, and *topB* (green and burgundy), Type IV secretion system components (*virB1–virB10*) (orange), and pilus assembly proteins *pilN* and *pilQ* (purple). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Schematic representation of AHPND-associated plasmids (*pVA1-kriznoit*, *pVA1-3HP*, and *pVpr14*) identified in *Vibrio campbellii* VP3. Conserved genetic elements, including PirAB toxin genes (yellow), IS5 transposases (pink), and hypothetical proteins (gray), are highlighted. The structural organization of these plasmids suggests a potential role in horizontal gene transfer and virulence dissemination.

et al., 2020).

The complete sequence of the pVA1-kriznoit plasmid revealed a highly conserved gene architecture with previously reported AHPND-associated plasmids (Wang et al., 2020; Gordils-Valentín et al., 2024), including the *pirAB* toxin genes flanked by IS5 transposases and several hypothetical proteins (Dong et al., 2017a; Xiao et al., 2017). This

structural conservation, together with the presence of conjugation-related genes and mobile genetic elements, underscores the high potential for horizontal transfer of virulence factors between species within the Harveyi clade (Dong et al., 2019 Wang et al., 2020; Yan et al., 2024). In this context, the phylogenetic proximity of *V. alginolyticus* and *V. parahaemolyticus* strains isolated from wild specimens of

Fig. 6. Sensitivity of *Nodipecten subnodosus* juveniles to *Vibrio campbellii* VP3, a causative strain of AHPND. Cumulative mortality curves over a 15-day exposure period to increasing bacterial concentrations (T1 to T4) of *V. campbellii* VP3 (expressed as CFU/mL). Values represent mean \pm standard deviation ($n = 3$). A significant difference in mortality is observed only in the highest concentration condition T4 (**** $p < 0.001$ vs all other treatments).

Table 2

Clinical observations and nested PCR detection of *pirAB* and 16S rRNA genes in pooled gill and stomach tissues from *Nodipecten subnodosus* juveniles experimentally infected with *Vibrio campbellii* carrying the AHPND-associated plasmid (pVA1). PCR was performed on five pools per tissue (two individuals per pool). (—) = Not analyzed.

Treatment	Inoculum concentration (CFU/mL)	Clinical observations	Gill PCR	Stomach PCR
T1	None	Day 1–15: Asymptomatic; active filtration; rapid valve closure to stimulus.	PirAB 0/5 16SARNr 5/5	—
T2	5×10^2 CFU/mL	Day 1–15: Asymptomatic; active filtration; rapid valve closure to stimulus	PirAB 4/5 16SARNr 5/5	—
T3	5×10^4 CFU/mL	Day 1–15: Asymptomatic; active filtration; rapid valve closure to stimulus	PirAB 5/5 16SARNr 5/5	—
T4	5×10^6 CFU/mL	Day 4: Lethargy, no feeding activity; Day 6: Partial mantle detachment, gill damage; Days 8–15: Moribund, slow valve closure, mortality.	PirAB 5/5 16SARNr 5/5	PirAB 2/5 16SARNr 5/5

N. subnodosus free of v_{CAHPND} -VP3 raises concerns about their potential role as recipients of such mobile plasmids, especially within host-associated microenvironments such as gill and gastrointestinal tissues where high bacterial densities and frequent interspecies interactions facilitate horizontal gene transfer (Yang et al., 2019; Xue et al., 2022; Bao et al., 2022). Critically, although these native strains do not carry *pirAB* genes, their genomic compatibility with pVA1-like elements suggests a latent risk of acquiring pathogenic traits, transforming commensal or opportunistic *Vibrio* spp. into highly virulent strains.

This study provides the first report of the potential experimental susceptibility of the scallop *N. subnodosus* to a *Vibrio* strain carrying the AHPND-associated virulence plasmid pVA1, originally isolated from *L. vannamei* mortality events in intensive shrimp farming systems in northern Peru. Previous research has shown that *Vibrio* strains causing AHPND from the Americas, including Peru, exhibit high pathogenicity towards *L. vannamei* (Kersanté et al., 2021; Beltrán et al., 2024). Although the present infection was experimentally induced, the possibility of natural interphylogenetic transmission cannot be excluded, raising concerns regarding the ecological and economic implications of such pathogens in bivalve aquaculture and coastal ecosystems. This is particularly relevant in Peru, where the Peruvian scallop *Argopecten purpuratus*, a closely related species farmed along the same coastal region, is among the three aquaculture species of greatest national economic importance (Ministerio de la Producción, 2023. Anuario Estadístico Pesquero y Acuicola 2022; Ministerio de la Producción (PRODUCE), 2022).

The immersion challenge to evaluate the susceptibility of juvenile *N. subnodosus* (mean shell height: 24.7 ± 0.84 mm; mean weight: 4.5 ± 1 g) revealed a dose-dependent response. No mortality was observed at 5×10^2 and 5×10^4 CFU/mL, whereas all individuals died by day 15 post-infection at the highest dose of 5×10^6 CFU/mL. However, analysis by qPCR confirmed the presence of plasmid copies in gill tissue, and the

Fig. 7. Assimilation assay (trial 2) of different bacterial strains by *Nodipecten subnodosus* juveniles. Assimilation curve of inoculum of *V. alginolyticus* (strain P12) and *V. campbellii* causing AHPND, based on the reduction of colony-forming units (CFU/mL) from water samples monitored every 30 min.

Fig. 8. Cumulative mortality curves of *Nodipecten subnodosus* juveniles exposed to *Vibrio alginolyticus* (4.5×10^6 CFU/mL), the AHPND-causing *V. campbellii* (5.1×10^6 CFU/mL) and an uninfected control group. Mortality was monitored over time, and species were compared using the Kruskal–Walli’s rank sum test, revealing significant differences among treatments ($\chi^2 = 20.062$, $df = 2$, $p = 4.401 \times 10^{-5}$).

pirAB toxin genes were detected even in animals exposed to sublethal doses. These findings aligned with those reported by Mendoza-Maldonado et al. (2018) in Catarina scallop *Argopecten ventricosus* where juveniles (mean shell height: 5.3 ± 1.1 mm) exposed to *V. parahaemolyticus* harboring the pVA1, showed a 100 % mortality within 48–96 h at 1×10^5 CFU/mL. Mortalities were much more rapid than those reported in the present study for *N. subnodosus* for the highest dose of 5×10^6 CFU/mL suggesting either differences in pathogens virulence or host susceptibility. Interestingly, adults *A. ventricosus* (shell height: 4.3 ± 0.57 cm) exhibited delayed mortality (up to 80 % by 144

h) and an LC_{50} of 6.2×10^4 CFU/mL (Mendoza-Maldonado et al., 2018).

Signs of lethargy, mantle damage, and gill deterioration before death were observable in experimental scallops exposed to the highest dose, which is consistent with the progression of acute bacterial infections in bivalves (Zannella et al., 2017) although the clinical signs observed were nonspecific and cannot be attributed solely to AHPND pathology. Notably, exposure to lower concentrations of v_C AHPND-VP3 led to subclinical infections, as evidenced by the detection of *pirAB* genes in gill and stomach tissues. These observations are consistent with findings in shrimp, where low-dose exposure results in asymptomatic carriers

Table 3

Quantification of the *pirAB* virulence plasmid (copies/ μ L) by qPCR using TaqMan probes across different treatments during the experimental infection of *Nodipecten subnodosus* with *Vibrio campbellii* harboring the AHPND-associated plasmid. The qPCR assay demonstrated high technical reliability, with amplification efficiencies ranging from 0.9953 to 0.9999 and correlation coefficients (R^2) exceeding 0.99, ensuring accurate and reproducible absolute quantification.

Treatment	Inoculum	Stock	Water – 0 h		Gill – 15d		
	(CFU/mL)	copies/ μ L	Cq	copies/ μ L	Cq	copies/ μ L	Cq
C+	5.6×10^8	3.35×10^6	14.5	–	–	7.22×10^6	14.92
Stock	5×10^8	8.92×10^5	19.7	–	–	–	–
T4	5×10^6	–	–	1.26×10^4	23.9	1.35×10^6	17.11
T3	5×10^4	–	–	3.28×10^2	30	5.52×10^3	24.29
T2	5×10^2	–	–	8.9×10	32.2	1.34×10^2	29.14
T1	0	–	–	–	–	–	–

Positive control (C⁺) corresponds to *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* DNA carrying *pirAB*.

capable of disseminating the pathogen (Tran et al., 2013; Han et al., 2015). This suggests that bivalves, including *N. subnodosus*, could act as environmental reservoirs of AHPND-causing vibrios under specific ecological conditions.

Due to their filter-feeding behavior and continuous exposure to the water column, bivalves are highly susceptible to the uptake and retention of suspended bacteria, including potential pathogens (Beaz-Hidalgo et al., 2010; Travers et al., 2015). In this study, bacterial assimilation assays confirmed the accumulation of *V. campbellii* in exposed *N. subnodosus* juveniles. Gill and stomach tissues were selected for molecular analysis based on their distinct physiological roles in pathogen-host interactions. In shrimp, the stomach is a primary target of AHPND pathogenesis, where PirAB toxins induce epithelial necrosis and structural disruption (Tran et al., 2013; Lee et al., 2015). Conversely, in bivalves, the gills serve both as respiratory and feeding organs, playing a central role in particle capture and microbial contact (Balcázar et al., 2006; Mendoza-Maldonado et al., 2018). Hence, assessing both tissues enabled a comprehensive evaluation of organ-specific colonization and provided evidence of *N. subnodosus* acting as a potential reservoir for *pirAB*-positive *Vibrio* under high-exposure conditions. These findings support the hypothesis that filter-feeding mollusks may contribute to the environmental persistence and dissemination of AHPND-associated vibrios, particularly in ecosystems affected by untreated effluents from shrimp farms.

The comparative trial revealed significant differences in pathogenicity between $v_{CAHPND-VP3}$ and native *V. alginolyticus* P12 isolates obtained from *N. subnodosus*. While $v_{CAHPND-VP3}$ exposure caused 100 % cumulative mortality, *V. alginolyticus* resulted in only 30 % mortality under the same conditions within the same period of time (15 days). These results suggest that the PirAB toxin plays a critical role in the pathogenicity of $v_{CAHPND-VP3}$ pathogenicity toward *N. subnodosus* likely contributing to its heightened virulence. Interestingly, both bacterial strains were similarly assimilated by scallops during the early hours post-infection, as confirmed by quantitative recovery and nested PCR. This indicates that the initial stages of bacterial colonization are not dependent on the presence of the pVA1 plasmid but that subsequent pathogenic effects could largely be mediated by toxin production.

The quantification of plasmid copies/ μ L in the bacterial inoculum revealed that the virulent $v_{CAHPND-VP3}$, at a concentration of 5×10^8 CFU/mL, contained approximately 8.92×10^5 copies/ μ L. In contrast, inoculum adjusted to 5×10^6 CFU/mL for experimental challenges contained 1.26×10^4 copies/ μ L, indicating significant plasmid loss. This instability has been documented in *V. parahaemolyticus* and other plasmid-bearing pathogens, often linked to transposase sequence alterations flanking the *pir* operon (Tinwongger et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2015; Wang et al 2020).

In the sensitivity trial, mortality occurred at a plasmid concentration of 1.35×10^6 copies/ μ L in gill tissues by day 15, with bacterial proliferation exceeding initial inoculum levels in T4 trial (5×10^6 CFU/mL). At lower inoculum concentrations (T2: 5×10^2 CFU/mL; T3: 5×10^4 CFU/mL), plasmid replication was observed in gill tissues (1.34×10^2

copies/ μ L and 5.52×10^3 copies/ μ L, respectively), but no mortality occurred. These findings suggest a critical plasmid copy threshold for pathogenicity and mortality, consistent with prior dose-response studies in *V. parahaemolyticus* (Soto-Rodríguez et al., 2015; Aranguren-Caro et al., 2020). The higher number of plasmid copies found in moribund animals (T4 trial) in relation to the initial inoculum could be either related to plasmid proliferation or AHPND causing bacteria multiplication.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates the susceptibility of *N. subnodosus* juveniles to *V. campbellii* strains harboring the AHPND-associated pVA1-type plasmid. Experimental infections revealed a dose-dependent increase in plasmid load (*pirAB* gene copies), with complete mortality at high bacterial loads and subclinical infections at lower concentrations, evidenced by the detection of *pirAB* genes in gill and stomach tissues. Comparative pathogenicity assays confirmed that mortality in *N. subnodosus* was associated with the presence of the *pirAB* genes, as the non-toxigenic *V. alginolyticus* strain caused significantly lower mortality despite similar assimilation rates. Whole genome sequencing confirmed the identity of the virulent strain as *V. campbellii*, and plasmid analysis revealed a conserved gene organization in pVA1-kriznoit, including *pirAB*, IS5 transposases, and conjugative elements. These genomic features, together with the phylogenetic proximity of native *Vibrio* spp. to $v_{CAHPND-VP3}$, underscore the risk of horizontal gene transfer in environments with high microbial density, such as those associated with filter-feeding bivalves. The results highlight the role of *N. subnodosus* as a potential reservoir of AHPND-causing vibrios and underline the need for targeted surveillance and improved aquaculture effluent management to mitigate pathogen dissemination.

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Krizia Pretell Monzón: Conceptualization, Investigation, Data curation, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Damaris Esquén Bayona:** Investigation, Resources, Data curation, Formal analysis. **Yuriko Saavedra Ríos:** Investigation, Data curation. **Frank Guzman Escudero:** Data curation, Formal analysis. **Judith**

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jip.2025.108404>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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